

When Memories Become Tangible

Jewelry as Physical Representations of Memories

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Abstract: This paper examines jewelry as a tangible form of memories. People carry memories of their lost loved ones in their pieces of jewelry, but to do this, they need to attach their intangible memories to the physical forms of jewelry. This paper examines the tangibility of memories in jewelry through American and Finnish women's stories about their meaningful jewelry. Its theoretical background lies in Durkheim's and Simmel's notions about how people use wearable things to communicate parts of themselves to others. It is based on a qualitative analysis of the stories women told me about their meaningful jewelry.

Key words: *Jewelry, Memory, Emotion, Family, Narrative*

1. Introduction

A woman I interviewed in Chicago told me how she cares about her bracelet touching her skin. With this physical touch she is able to reminisce about experiences in her life. The well-known design of Tiffany & Co. silver bracelet with a heart charm is related to some of her most painful memories. She said that with the physical touch of the bracelet she is able to go back to these very personal experiences and handle the sadness she faced years ago. This paper analyzes how jewelry and memories of strong emotions intertwine. Especially powerful emotions such as sadness, sorrow and yearning after someone are the topic of this paper. Often pieces of jewelry are related to other people in our lives; they are purchased to act as mementos, they are received as gifts from important people, or they are inherited. Through processes like these, pieces of jewelry may come to act as mediators for people. They may also act as mediators to those occasions where the transaction occurred and possession was gained, such as a funeral rite where family jewelry was inherited.

This paper discusses woeful emotions evoked by wearing and possessing jewelry. Often these woeful emotions are perpetuated in memories that people carry with them in the physical form of jewelry. Not every piece of jewelry has a negative emotional connotation. Jewelry is often related to important and meaningful things like promotions, weddings or other happy moments in women's lives. However, based on the stories studied in this

paper, in many cases, the jewelry is also related to sadness and longing. With jewelry, people construct memories of events which were emotional. Often the memories become stronger than the original emotion was [8].

Thus, often memories people attach to their jewelry are related not only to the history of the jewelry but also to the history of the possessor. This is particularly true for jewelry received as gifts in ritualistic family related occasions. They are also worn in similar occasions; therefore the memories attached to the jewelry consist of memories of the family members, both those who are still alive but also those who have passed away. In fact, the memories may also be about people never met by the current possessors of the piece of jewelry.¹ In their study of possessions, Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton concluded that people consider things special when they are related to other, important people [3]. Similarly, as the stories in this paper will show, meaningful and special pieces of jewelry are mediators to other people and loved ones. The memories of loved ones are handed down through time as jewelry is passed to the next possessors. These memories are handed down through stories. With these memories, a piece of jewelry gains a biography that lasts over decades and may cover significant chunks of family histories.

2. What is Jewelry?

There are several theories that can illustrate the link between jewelry and family history. According to the sociologist Georg Simmel, jewelry is worn to adorn oneself [10]. People are willing to adorn themselves not only to please themselves but also to please others who see them with the jewelry. Simmel has stated after his study of fashion of the European upper class about a century ago that people adorn themselves to please viewers and to express their own social status. According to Simmel, wearables of different social classes vary. The highest class creates and changes fashions first. After the high class has set the fashion it is available for the lower classes. When the lower class adopts the fashion, the upper class is not anymore following it, but it is already creating new shifts in fashion. His statement, in other words, is that with fashion one shows the social class in which one belongs to [10].

The problem with this theory is that today, fashion is not adapted as clearly from the upper classes to the lower classes anymore since the classes in societies are not that clear. Especially in the societies in which the data studied for this paper was gathered, in Finland which has the lowest socio-economic differences in the world, and the United States, which has no traditional upper class. Nevertheless, there are similarities in adorning today to adorning a century ago. Women are still having a dialog with the people surrounding them using jewelry as mediators in the dialog. Nowadays women are not necessarily showing only their social class with jewelry but they are still expressing their kinship by means of adornments.

Simmel's contemporary Emile Durkheim [4] made several remarks about the reasons to wear and possess jewelry in his study of the origins of religion in archaic societies. For Durkheim, jewelry was worn as totemic items. In archaic societies, totems provided kinships with a means of identification. Different kinships had their own totemic item meaning that members of that kinship were part of an established group, often having the same

¹ We talk about the possessor of jewelry rather than the owner: the value of family jewelry lies in having it and passing it on to the next generation, not in its value on the market.

bloodline. Only members of that particular kinship had the right to use the symbol of the totem. Totemic items were worn and used as a sign to express being part of a particular kinship for not only the wearers but also for the viewers. Importantly, totemic functions went beyond identification: totems were also a means of gaining the powers from kin and, for example, the animal the sign represented. Signs of totemic items such as turtles or the sun were placed visibly, engraved into tools, embroidered into clothes, and worn as independent items as jewelry. According to Durkheim, the totemic items were not possessed by the individual members of the kinship, but by the kinship itself, and its members had the right to use them and gain advantage through use. Others could easily interpret one's social relations through her jewelry when it represented a totemic item. [4]

Later, Ervin Goffman studied roles in everyday life [5]. His notion about the setting in which we take and play out our everyday roles is important when discussing wearing and possessing jewelry. Based on Goffman, the setting includes the whole product entity surrounding us as well as e.g. language we choose to use. Everything in this setting, from the interior of the home to the wearable, influences the conclusion of which role we are in and also the actions in the role. Pieces of jewelry are part of this setting, but at the same time they act as symbols of social status [6]. According to Goffman's study on social status symbols, jewelry plays an important role in how people communicate about themselves to others. With jewelry women may indicate their marital status, style, level of income, focus of interest, ethnic background, hobbies, or lifestyle. Erving Goffman discusses status symbols as items designating the position one has in society. They are worn followed by rules that have evolved over time and which are universal. Having products as status symbols is somewhat universal but it varies by culture in terms of appearance and ways of wearing and having status symbols. Based on Goffman's study, a status symbol can be a product, wearable, or way of behavior, e.g. style of language one uses [6].

Even though these theories date from far back in the last century, they help us focus on several features that are still relevant today. In particular, the reasons to wear and possess jewelry do not differ too much from the times when Simmel, Durkheim and Goffman concluded their studies. People are still expressing their social statuses through jewelry just as in Simmel's Berlin, even though the hierarchical class system typical to the Belle Epoque Germany and France is long gone, and fashion tends to come from the streets rather than the upper classes. Even though modern society is more individualistic than the archaic ones studied in Durkheim's oeuvre, people still relate to their family and other social groups through jewelry. Thus, although people in modern societies have many ways to express kinships, social status and bloodlines including names, nationalities, professions, and physical places, we are still willing to express our belonging and connectedness with our adornments.

3. Data

The data studied for this paper is from two sources. The preliminary data is 464 stories gathered from Finnish women by the Kalevala Women's Association in 2007. The association gathered the stories via a writing competition in an effort to preserve Finnish oral history. They asked people to write about their meaningful jewelry without any further rules for the competition. This made the stories diverse; the data is very rich and versatile. Even though the number of stories is high, the qualitative approach has been applied to preserve the

biography of the jewelry as told in the stories. Analysis was done by clustering the contents of the stories in an effort to find similarities and differences in the contents.

Based on insights from the preliminary data described above, a self-documentation study with 28 women in Helsinki, Finland, and Chicago, Illinois, USA was conducted. This study was inspired by the Design Probes methodology [9]. The self-documentation kits included cards with questions about the jewelry participants were wearing each day. They were also asked to illustrate their wearables on the picture of a paper doll and to take photos of themselves wearing the jewelry (Figure 1). The participants documented their everyday life with their jewelry for nine days, including both weekends and weekdays. After nine days of self-documentation, the kits were received, the photos developed, and the kits were studied thoroughly. The information provided by the participants via the self-documentation kits were used as the basis and starting point for in-depth interviews. The self-documentation kits acted as sensitizing media before the in-depth interviews were conducted. With the self-documentation kits and the interviews women shared various kinds of stories related to jewelry. The interviews were mostly conducted at participants' homes near their jewelry box. When women were pulling jewelry out of their jewelry boxes during the interviews, they often came up with many new stories to tell. Touching a particular piece of jewelry instead of just reminiscing about it seemed to be essential for remembering the nuances in the history of the jewelry.

All the quotations in this paper are from the stories women shared, wrote or told during the interviews, and all the pictures are by the author.

Figure.1 The self-documentation kits included disposal cameras and nine cards to write the stories and illustrate the jewelry and wearables of the day.

According to the stories one piece of jewelry may contain a number of different memories connected to emotions. Because of that they evoke many emotions when possessors wear them. Pleasant memories related to the jewelry make the usage and the user experience of the jewelry more pleasant; they bring the nice memories to mind and therefore influence the amount of time they are worn. However, not all memories related to jewelry are pleasant; sometimes people do not want to possess jewelry linked to unpleasant memories. Often, though, the hard unpleasant memories are so important that the jewelry is kept, even if it is not worn. In the stories, various emotions are related to jewelry. Common to all emotions related to jewelry is that they are strong, not weak. As in Katz's study of emotions [8], when people talk about jewelry, they create memories around emotions strong in intensity, not around weak emotions that characterize everyday life.

4. Tangibility, bereavement and memories

Each time when there is a loss in a family, some undefined amount of time for mourning is needed [7]. Often women who faced the loss of a loved one told me how jewelry had played an important role in the time of mourning. Since people relate themselves to their family and friends through physical artifacts such as jewelry, they are important artifacts when life is reconstructed after the loss of a close person. Wearing and possessing jewelry related to past generations does not necessarily make people remember their lost ones, but with the physical artifacts they are able to manage the memories in order to handle the grief. Sometimes people keep their lost family members with them in physical form by wearing jewelry reminiscent of them. Sometimes jewelry related to lost loved ones arouses such painful emotions in the wearer's mind that it cannot be worn, and is just held in safe keeping.

A woman received a charm bracelet from her husband after losing their twin daughters in premature labor (Figure 2). She engraved their names on the heart shaped charm in the bracelet to have them always with her. As she says in the following quotation, she would not forget them but she wanted to have them with her physically. This mass-produced piece of jewelry became sacred for the possessor not only because of the memory connected to it but also because of the physical engraving. Durkheim describes how some possessions become sacred because of the spirit they carry from the death [4]. Similarly, this woman made her bracelet sacred by attaching intangible memories to it and making the tangible and visual engraving of the names of her lost twin daughters in it.

“I was pregnant before I had my daughter ... and I was pregnant with twins and... when I was five months pregnant I went into labour and they didn't survive. So we had two girls and we had to bury them and all that. (...) I also got this from my husband. It's a bracelet with a heart with their names on it. So that was right after that happened. (...) I wanted to have something to ... not to remember, because I would always remember but, I wanted to have something close to me. For some reason, that they would be close to me. So, when we baptized them we gave them these names and so, I put their names on the heart on the bracelet and I would wear it everyday. Just to kind of have them with me.”

Figure.2 This charm bracelet is possessed by a woman who lost her twin daughters in premature labor. She is carrying the physical memory of the daughters in this bracelet. For her, touching the bracelet makes the memory of the daughters alive and tangible.

Another woman's story is about a medallion she had got from her first boyfriend after their first date when they were young. Also, this medallion is sacred [4] and works as a mediator of a lost loved one. Since the medallion and the memory are already aged enough, she has made a plan for the future of the medallion. It will be given to the person in the family who reminds her most of him. Often there are "regulations" in a family about how particular pieces of jewelry ought to be handed down to the next possessors [1]. For example, in some families a wedding ring goes always to the oldest daughter on her wedding day. The following story tells how the previous possessor of a confirmation rite medallion was Pekka, the teller's boyfriend, who got it from his grandmother as a confirmation gift in order to give it to his loved one. The current possessor, now a grandmother, is going to give it to her grandson, also named Pekka, on his confirmation day with the same wish that he would one day give it to the one he loves.

"I did not want my mother to see me walking down the street holding hands with a boy. I turned to teacher Uimonen's yard from the corner of Suonionkatu street and told Pekka that it was also the way to our yard. I forbade him to come further than Uimonen's gate. Pekka asked me to wait and opened his coat. He took the medallion necklace from his neck and placed it around mine. "I have gotten this from my grandmother as a Confirmation present and my grandmother said that I can one day give it to the girl I fall in love with."

Two years after receiving the medallion on their first date he drowned on their sailing trip. During mourning for him, the medallion became a mediating thing to Pekka and to the times they spent together. The medallion became a means to process the sorrow and grief. Later the medallion worked as a tangible object she could use to remember the times she was in love with her boyfriend. The medallion not only represents Pekka to her, but also to her family.

“Sorrow affected me deeply. I did not go studying that year. At night when I could not sleep I held my medallion and felt Pekka near me, he had turned into my life’s angel. We often reminisced upon Pekka at home, and then grandma said that the jewellery would always speak to me about its wearer.”

This woman is also illustrating the importance of physical touch of jewelry. As she mentions, touch helped her to process the sorrow when transforming the heart-rending incident into memory. Now, after decades of this heart-rending incident, she has a grandson who will soon be the next owner of this medallion and will be honored to store the memory through the physical artifact. This medallion, like the charm discussed earlier, is a mass produced, affordable piece of jewelry, but it has become sacred and particular with the memories it symbolizes.

“I got a grandson 35 years after the incident. I have often visited the Ristikangas cemetery with him. When he was little I told him about all the loved ones who we brought flowers to. Little Pekka listened carefully and found those sleeping under the cemetery grass from our photo albums as soon as he learned to read. He won a Junior sailing competition on a small sailing boat at age 7.

Next Sunday is his Confirmation day. I will give him the Madonna medallion, which I would not give to anyone else because jewellery speaks of its wearer.”

These two pieces of jewelry, the charm bracelet and the medallion, are used as objects to process mourning, sorrow and yearning after someone. In their stories, women tell how they need tangible artifacts not only for storing the stories and memories of lost loved ones but also for managing intense emotions associated with the stories. As a rule, those pieces of jewelry that are carriers of memories of strong emotions have to be well-kept to be handed down to the next possessor in a family. Nevertheless, whether they are worn or not, the physical body of the jewelry has to be maintained as does the memory. Akin to Belk, who discusses the tragedy of losing meaningful possessions [2], fear of losing jewelry that holds such strong memories can be a burden for the possessors. Women tell how they are afraid of losing the piece of jewelry and memories, and that is why keeping it very safe is the most important method of tending to the possessions. Thus, women also tell about how they take care of jewelry, repairing it when needed, and storing it. They either wear these meaningful pieces of jewelry every day, or keep them safe, hardly ever wearing them. Hallam and Hockey, who have studied objects and practices that remind us of loved ones we have lost, describe how for constructing memories after a loss, the human mind needs material grounding [7]. This can be also seen in the stories presented in this paper. The

possessors of the charm bracelet and the medallion ground their memories of lost ones in physical form in jewelry.

5. Conclusions

In this paper we have argued that as tangible physical products, pieces of jewelry also have intangible features which are meaningful and evocative for the possessors. According to the stories studied for this paper, these intangible features are often valued far more than the actual product as such. The intangible features built from past emotions and transmitted in memories turn jewelry into something sacred for the possessor. They also give meaning to the piece and a reason to possess it. These meaningful pieces of jewelry are not always worn, but they are carefully kept for the future. With the physical piece of jewelry, the possessor is able to hand down the intangible memories to the next possessor [1].

In this paper we have presented heartbreaking stories in which jewelry plays a key role. In the first case, the charm bracelet was purchased in order to become a memento. The possessor wanted to have something tangible touching her body to have the lost twin daughters with her. So, her husband got this charm bracelet for her and got it engraved with the names of the twins. She has worn this bracelet for years to have the daughters close to her. She values the physical touch of the bracelet. The other story is about a medallion that belonged to the current possessor's first boyfriend Pekka's family. She got it because it was to be given to the first girl Pekka fell in love with. Pekka drowned two years after giving her the medallion. She hasn't given it to anyone yet but will soon give it to her grandson with the same wish: that he one day give it to a girl he falls in love with. In both of these stories jewelry is a tool for bringing intense emotions from the past to the present. Jewelry also works as tools for the possessors to work through sorrow and sadness brought about by loss. Jewelry is tangible and mobile; it gives a physical form to the possessors' memories and emotions embedded in these memories [7].

Pieces of jewelry connect possessors to their family through generations in late modern societies just like they did in archaic societies according to Durkheim [4]. As our stories vividly show, women create a connection between loved ones who have passed on and jewelry they carry. The connections to the dead loved ones are not always visible to others, but they are always available as memories for the possessors themselves.

6. Discussion

As design and craft products, pieces of jewelry are a little seen but essential part of people's lives and human material culture. Since people tend to carry the memories of lost people in their jewelry, many pieces of jewelry come to have long and extensive biographies. As intangible features of jewelry, memories are construed of emotionally intense periods in the possessors' lives. Memories of strong emotions linked to jewelry make them "sticky" in possessors' lives and family for long periods of time. As such, these processes are beyond design, but may be considered when designing new products for the market.

Above all, this study shows that jewelry is significant to people, but that it is people who create the meanings and emotions that make pieces significant. The problem is that these meanings and emotions are as complex as life itself, and can hardly be foreseen. This analysis, then, suggests that humbleness is a good policy for designers.

Designers need not take on the burden of being foretellers. If there is a policy we can suggest, it is that it is good not to overdo design, but let it be open to life and its interpretations. This observation has many implications to the design of physical forms as well as interactions, but also and above all, to symbolic structures behind design, and therefore thinking and research in the designers' mind.

Turned into a design philosophy, our observations go against many things in the market, but not necessarily against revolutionary designs. Often jewelry is designed to be in constant physical touch with the wearer and to last forever. The appearance of most pieces changes with the time and the fashion, but mainstream jewelry design follows traditional forms, and for good reason. The logic is that as the piece of jewelry should last in usage for long time, it has to be timeless. Also, most jewelry made with the traditional skills and craftsmanship of goldsmiths is physically made to last decades, even centuries. To use a technical metaphor, timelessness and durability provide a good "platform" for attaching memories. However, even if the jewelry is designed to last forever, the designer or the goldsmith cannot usually influence whether they become tangible forms for memories. On the other hand, when the jewelry is produced to be timeless, it has a good chance to become a platform for emotions and memories. However, it can also become meaningless due to its cliché-like and non-personal design.

Herein lies the irony: although jewelry is often designed and produced to be long-lasting, it does not come with the emotional content that make it worth keeping and handing down. Still, being long-lasting products and in constant physical touch with the wearer, pieces of jewelry have a good chance of becoming such containers. The question is how to find designs that provide both for longevity and timelessness, as well as for personality and uniqueness. Part of the answer of course lies in the craftsmanship – every handmade piece is unique – but this is not the whole story. After all, some pieces of jewelry have come to be something far more than personal adornments despite the fact that they were industrially manufactured. A more important answer lies in "scar-like" imperfections and modifications that have become physical marks for emotionally laden memories. This train of thought suggests that designers could do well in providing room for life and its marks in design. It is a question of being subtle, understated, and even discreet, rather than just following tradition or rebelling against it with quirky designs. Although the designer cannot know if a piece of jewelry will become meaningful for its future possessors, she can nevertheless consider this as a possibility during the design process, and provide space for these meanings.

Should one build a design research agenda on our observations, it would lead to studies of subtle emotions, meanings, and other things that give access to life histories, real or introspective. Such life histories are a rich source of inspiration, and differ from more artistic and traditional alternatives. Thus, although this paper cannot give straightforward design solutions for jewelry, it gives insights into how women story their world and emotions with their jewelry. This analysis gives us tools to observe jewelry and see its connection to life, both in emotional and social terms. These are typically downplayed in education in jewelry, which is typically anchored in craft and tradition, and usually sees products in individualistic terms. If followed, our analysis would lead to a design program that would add sensitivity to the complexity of emotions in social relationships to technical skills, historical understanding, and artistic sensibility. Jewelry may not be as complex as life itself, but it is for life.

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